

ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PRACTICING PSYCHOLOGIST IN SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *This article describes the activities of a practicing psychologist in schools and his role in the organization of psychological services and the creation of a social environment in schools.*

Keywords: *environment, school, practice, psychologist, ethics, aesthetics, community, class, culture.*

Introduction: It is known that the socialization of a person mainly corresponds to the school years. Therefore, one of the main tasks of the school is to create all the conditions for the development of the child, to introduce the most appropriate forms of education and upbringing, taking into account his individual and psychological characteristics. But everyone knows that in the current conditions, the school faces many problems and unresolved issues, all of which require the school's support from all sides. In recent years, based on the instructions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tasks of determining the abilities of young people from an early age, developing their talents in all directions, the need for an individual approach to the student, and differential education are required. Accordingly, it creates a number of problems for the school and the public. Examination of knowledge by means of tests, admission to higher educational institutions and all branches of education through tests requires the immediate establishment of psychological services. Taking into account the demands that social psychology puts on the school of our time, taking into account the difficulties it is experiencing these days, it has:

- a) understand them;
- b) scientific analysis;
- c) prevention;
- d) looking for ways and setting the task of providing guidance.

What can school psychologists do? They are:

1. The psychological service established in the school should first of all ask the psychologist to thoroughly study the conditions of that school, determine the individual and group working methods depending on the characteristics of each age group.

2. The school psychologist should fully study the cases of withdrawal from mental development among children and analyze the social and psychological conditions that caused it.

3. The school psychologist should have a form of information compiled on the basis of test results and scientific analyzes of children of different ages regarding their abilities and interest in the profession. Based on this information, the psychologist should develop specific instructions related to approaching children individually, organizing additional classes for some of them, developing children's abilities in cooperation with school and family.

4. The school psychologist should determine the psychological environment related to the mutual relations between the mental states of individual classes in the school. He should deeply study the relationship between official and unofficial leaders and give the necessary guidance to the school administration to the deputy director for educational affairs.

5. In addition, the school psychologist should organize consultations on measures to prevent various conflicts, conflicts and disorders, to study their nature. Such consultations are organized separately for parents and a team of pedagogues. Another aspect of the activity of a

practical psychologist is to provide consultation and assistance to the teaching team on various issues.

Based on the above tasks, the school psychologist can determine the main directions of activity. They are:

- diagnostic and corrective work (restrictions in any developmental process, finding solutions to situations of lagging behind, preventing them), psycho-prophylactic work (psychohygiene, creating conditions that ensure normal psychological development of the child);
- psychological consultations, raising the psychological literacy of teachers, parents and students;
- adapting the methods used in psychology to specific conditions, using them effectively;
- systematically analyze the collected scientific data;
- it consists of creating tests, scientifically justifying their sensitivity, and preparing scientific conclusions and instructions by regularly checking the abilities of each child and the knowledge of teachers with the help of tests.

We believe that the improvement of psychological services for schools in our Republic will contribute to the preparation of our future children for the great and glorious tasks before the society.

Conclusion: Society in general has a lot of demands on the science of psychology. In order to satisfy them, in our republic, first of all, it is time to develop extensive scientific research and apply their results to bold practice. The connection between theory and practice is one of the main tasks of psychologists.

REFERENCES:

1. Akbarova, N., & Azamatov, Z. (2023). *Deformation measurement by digital holographic interferometry. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 434, p. 01039). EDP Sciences.*
2. Bafoevich, U. B., Rasulovna, K. R. N., & Ziyodulloevna, K. S. (2021). *REACTION OF 1, 1, 1-TRIFLUOROMETHYL-4-PHENYLBUTANEDIONE-2, 4 WITH BENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDE. INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN INDUSTRY, 9(3), 939-944.*
3. Dilafruz, Y., Odina, N., & Otabek, K. (2023). *EFFECT OF THE FUNGUS STIGMINA CARPOPHILA (LEV) ON ALMOND FRUIT WEIGHT. American Journal of Technology and Applied Sciences, 16, 1-3.*
4. Khujaev, O., Obidjanov, D., Tursunov, O., & Nazarova, O. (2021, December). *Types and composition of diseases and pests of restructured forest and pasture plants in the dry part of the Aral Sea. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 939, No. 1, p. 012084). IOP Publishing.*
5. Kochkarova, R. R., & Turgunov, E. (2023). *IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING CHEMISTRY LESSONS AT SCHOOL WITH THE HELP OF DIFFERENT GAMES. American Journal of Applied Science and Technology, 3(10), 15-19.*
6. M.Z. Kuvatova, Sh.A. Turdiyeva, R.R. Kochkarova. (2023). *USE OF VENN DIAGRAM AND NETWORK METHOD IN TEACHING THE TOPIC OF "IMPORTANT*

CLASSES OF INORGANIC COMPOUNDS" TEACHING METHODOLOGY IMPROVEMENT. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(10). Retrieved from <https://www.ijmrd.in/index.php/imjrd/article/view/223>

7. Nazarova, O., Khujaev, O., & Jumanazarov, G. (2023, March). *Septoria (Septoria pistaciae Desm.) pathogen infecting pistachio nuts in Uzbekistan and its biological characteristics*. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1142, No. 1, p. 012051). IOP Publishing.

8. Nurumbetova, S. (2022). VAIN ASPECTS OF PRACTICAL RELIGIOUS EXAMINATION IN THE INVESTIGATION OF CRIMES RELATED TO PROHIBITED RELIGIOUS MATERIALS. *Science and Innovation*, 1(6), 108-113.

9. Nurumbetova, S. (2022). ДИНИЙ МАЗМУНДАГИ ТАҚИҚЛАНГАН МАТЕРИАЛЛАР БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚ ЖИНОЯТЛАРНИ ТЕРГОВ ҚИЛИШДА ДИНШУНОСЛИК ЭКСПЕРТИЗАСИНИ ЎТКАЗИШ АМАЛИЁТИНИНГ МУҲИМ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(С6), 108-113.

10. Otajanova, M. (2021). A UNIQUE ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION OF THE ETHNOCULTURAL VALUES OF THE TURKIC PEOPLES. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(06), 108-115.

11. Rasulovna, K. R. (2023). *Complex Nickel (Ii) Compounds Based on Acyhydrazones of Aroyltrifluoroacetylmethhanes*. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(10), 3-5.

12. Tursunov, O., Dobrowolski, J. W., Khujaev, O., Abduganiev, N., Nazarova, O. J., & Yuldosheva, D. J. (2021, December). *Study on the perspectives of application of eco-friendly laser biotechnology for environmental protection in Uzbekistan*. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 939, No. 1, p. 012083). IOP Publishing.

13. Yuldashev Sanjarbek Arslon o'g'li. (2023). *The Solution of Economic Tasks with the Help of Probability Theory*. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 26, 26–29. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjet/article/view/4654>

14. Рузимбаев, С. Р., & Сабирова, Н. Э. (2019). Эпические певцы-сказительницы. In *Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера* (No. 32, pp. 22-24). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.

15. Сабирова, Н. Э. (2022). ПОСЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬНОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ ИСКУССТВА БАХШИ ХОРЕЗМА. *Universum: филология и искусствоведение*, (4 (94)), 36-40.

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